

Electronic Resources Awareness and Use by Students of Federal Polytechnic Oko

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Abstract

The study examined awareness and use of electronic resources by students in the Federal Polytechnic Oko library. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. A descriptive survey research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study comprised all 108 registered HND 1 and HND 2 undergraduate students of the department of Library Science and Information Science. A purposive sampling technique was used to select 108 users of the library from the population. Mean and standard deviation were used in answering the research questions while t-test was used to test the postulated null hypotheses. The result revealed that there is a significant influence of e-books and e-journals on students' awareness of online information resources, but there was no significant influence of online databases on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko library. The null hypotheses were rejected for e-books and e-journals while it was accepted for online databases. The study concluded that increasing awareness and training of students on how to use electronic resources is crucial. Recommendations on how to alleviate the problems of electronic resources indices and students' awareness of online information resources were also made.

Keywords: Electronic resources, Students, Polytechnic

Introduction

Electronic resources (or e-resources) are materials in digital format accessible electronically. E-resources are defined, as a resource which requires computer access or any electronic product that delivers a collection of data, be it text referring to full-text bases, electronic journals (e- journal), electronic books (e-books), online databases in varied digital formats, adobe acrobat documents (.pdf), webpages (.htm, .html, .asp etc.) and more. These materials are encoded for reading and manipulation by a computer, by the use of a peripheral device directly connected to the computer, such as a CD-ROM drive, or remotely via a network, such as the internet (Reitz, 2004). It is a combination of those resources that are 'born digital' and 'made digital'. According to AACR2 (2005), an electronic resource is: "Material (data and/or program(s)) encoded for manipulation by a computerized device. This material may require the use of a peripheral device directly connected to a computerized device (e.g. the internet)."

Electronic resources are resources in which information is stored electrically and are accessible through electronic systems and networks. There are a lot of advantages to Electronic resources which are not only to the librarians but also to the users, authors, editors, publishers, and archivists like simultaneous and instantaneous access, enormous time saving, easy search options, etc. Therefore, electronic resources

in its all surroundings include all kinds of digital collections in the form of e-books, e-databases, e-journals, electronic theses and dissertations, e-reports, etc. In a comprehensible way, an e-book is a book, or text, that has been created in, or converted to, a digital form. E-books are in all electronic versions of printed books. According to Davis (1997), an e-book is a written work readable on a computer screen, downloaded to a personal computer or digital assistant or placed on a reader designed for that purpose for professionally produced and edited text in an electronic format. On the other hand, the librarians' view of e-books is "any piece of electronic text regardless of size or composition (a digital object), but excluding journal publications, made available electronically (or optically) for any device (handheld or desk-bound) that includes a screen" (Chris, Louise & Ray, 2002). An e-book differs from a book in print as it requires some kind of electronic device to read.

Awareness is the knowledge that exists or understanding of a situation or subject at the present time based on information or experience (Ani & Ahiauzu, 2008). Awareness precedes use. Though, a fundamental factor in electronic information resources utilization is the 'perceived' information need, awareness of the existence of an electronic resource is a major determinant of use. Awareness of the availability of electronic resources is therefore an important variable that has been found to have a positive association with use of online information resources. Specifically, lack of awareness is among the primary reasons for under-utilizing electronic resources by students. This implies that though a student may identify his/her area of information need, without proper awareness of how and where to get electronic resources that will provide the information needed, such needs may not be met. Therefore, awareness is important if students are to harness these resources. The objective of this study is to ascertain the relationship between electronic resources use and students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko. The specific objectives of the study are:

1. Determining the relationship between e-books and students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko.
2. Determining the relationship between online databases and students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko.

Research Questions

The following are the research questions used in this research;

1. Is there any relationship between awareness and use of e-books in Federal Polytechnic Oko?
2. Is there any relationship between awareness and use of online databases in Federal Polytechnic Oko?

Hypotheses

The following are the hypotheses which are to be tested in this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between e-books and students' awareness of online information resources in Polytechnic Oko.
2. There is no significant relationship between online databases and students' awareness of online information resources in Federal Polytechnic Oko.

Review of Literature

According to Saye (2001), "Electronic resources are the resources that are generated through some electronic medium and made available to a wide range of viewers both on-site and off-site via some electronic transferring machine or internet." Electronic resources are systems in which information is stored electronically and made accessible through electronic systems and computer networks. These resources include OPAC, CD- ROMs, Online- Databases, E-journals E-books, Internet resources, etc. Multiple accesses speed, richer in content, reuse, timeliness, and anywhere access is some of the features of e-resources. Electronic resources are regarded as the mines of information that are explored through modern ICT devices, refined and redesigned and more often stored in cyberspace in the most concrete and compact form and can be accessed simultaneously from infinite points by a great number of audiences. Electronic resources and services refer to the variety of electronic and digital sources of information available to teachers and learners within an academic context. The change in traditional document delivery services, from print to electronic, has come about very quickly and libraries and information services have undergone significant transformation in order to effectively deliver electronic resources to the academic community.

The following features are the scope of e-resources:

- Electronic resources are not localized.
- They can be used from anywhere by the user and the user need not know where it is geographically located.
- It can be used simultaneously by many users at the same time.
- It is easy to copy and download them in user file.
- It reduces the distance between the user and the librarian.
- It creates global marketing environment.
- They are less bulky; very flexible; easy to revise, rearrange, reformat and combine with other documents (Chandra, 2007).

Students are being exposed because of electronic resources to a wide variety of online information resources and also opens up opportunities for learning because they enable learners to access, extend, transform and share ideas and information easily. Recently, polytechnics and librarians have been increasing the numbers of electronic resources in their collection, as e- books are becoming essential components in polytechnic library collections. Brophy (1993) detailing the advantages of electronic resources over traditional print-based sources stated that electronic resources are often faster than

consulting print indexes especially when searching retrospectively, and they are more straightforward when wishing to use combinations of keywords. They open up the possibility of searching multiple files at one time; can be printed and searches saved to be repeated at a later date; they are updated more often than the printed tools.

Electronic resources offer today's students different opportunities from their predecessors.

Brophy (1993) details the advantages of electronic resources for users as follows:

- The information needed can be delivered from the most appropriate source to the user.
- The user can re-specify his or her needs dynamically.
- The information is obtained when it is wanted, so becomes "just in time" rather than "just in case".
- The user selects only the information needed to answer the specific question.
- Equally the information is only stored should the user wish.

Electronic resources can therefore provide a number of advantages over traditional print-based sources (Ray & Day, 1997). The electronic resources are often faster than consulting print indexes, especially when searching retrospectively, they are more straightforward when wishing to use combinations of keywords, and they open up the possibility for searching multiple files at one time, a feat accomplished more easily than when using printed equivalents, electronic resources can be printed and searches saved to be repeated at a later date, they are updated more often than printed tools. One main advantage, especially to distance learners or those with limited time to access the library is their availability from outside the library by dial-up access. Optimal access to information resources and ICT literacy are increasingly essential for maximizing human capital potential.

The use of computer services by students are increasing in services such as the internet for their various educational needs because it enables them to have access to the array of learning opportunities offered by diverse of electronic sources (Siddique, 2004). The benefits of electronic sources to undergraduates in Nigerian University remain largely unused. According to Idowu (2004), some of the benefits include computer mediated communication and remote access to information sources for academic work. Electronic sources of information have changed the way knowledge and learning is acquired and has opened huge opportunities for undergraduates in universities. The opportunities created by electronic information resources in the enhancement of academic work enable students to lay their hands on abundant electronic resources at a click of few buttons. On-line search engines such as Google, Yahoo, and MSN and others, allow the users to identify and select different database, information base and equally download volumes of information into digital storage devices within a short time. Thus, skills required to maximize the potential of electronic resources, Dutton (1990) is of the view that much greater skill is required to use the electronic sources, and these skills include a knowledge of the structure of the database and the instructions which must be input into the computer by the searcher, as well as an understanding of the ways in which the instructions are linked with one another.

Hence, it is pertinent to note that the ability to find and retrieve information effectively is a transferable skill useful for future life as well as enabling the positive and successful use of the electronic resources in future. The acquisition of information skills is therefore to be seen as one of the key learning objectives for every student to be fully equipped to cope with the information intensive world – the information society as an end user. This is seen as the most recent development in information technology, Electronic resources can be seen as such and are among the most powerful tools ever invented in human history. Electronic resources are becoming more and more important for the academic community. Electronic resources offer today's students different opportunities compared to their predecessors. Liew, Foo and Chennupati (2000) argue that while reading an e-journal is not the same as reading a printed one, many are beginning to acknowledge the possibility that electronic documents offer users advanced features and novel form of functionality beyond what is possible in printed form.

E-books and Students' Awareness of Online Information Resources

E-book is a book-length publication in digital form, consisting of text, images, or both, readable on computers or other electronic devices, although sometimes defined as "an electronic version of a printed book". Many attempts have been made to classify the types of e-book. For example, Hawkins (2000) categorized e-books into four different types according to their accessibility whereas Crawford (2000) identified nine types of e-books based on various facets including their formats, standard, and length of content. E-books can also be characterized in terms of how the e-book can be displayed or read: on a computer through a network; a standalone desktop PC, notebook or PDA; using e-book reader software (e.g. Adobe Acrobat eBook reader); on a dedicated hardware device (e.g. an eBookman); or via the web; Chen (2000), on the other hand, defines e-books in terms of four perspectives: media, device, delivery and content.

An e-book is a text and image-based publication in digital form produced on published by and readable on computers, other digital devices. E-books are usually read on dedicated hardware devices known as e-readers or e-book devices. E-books are very useful tool for academic teachers, students etc. Many users now read the books on mobile phone by use of e-book reader software. E-books are preferred by the users for their features like changeable font size, make citation, links to other relevant sites, searching, sending to other users etc. E-books can be transferred from library catalogue to user's e-book readers for a fixed loan period and after which it is automatically taken back. E-books entrance into the field of education indicates the development of education and creation of the possibility to learn for everyone, anywhere and anytime (Biranvand & Khasseh, 2014). This may be due to the fact that readers of e-books are able to find a certain topic in an e-book much easier and effective than in a printed one (Gibson & Gibb, 2011).

Online Databases and Students' Awareness of Online Information Resources

An online database is an organized collection of large information, of a particular subject or various subject areas. The information of an online database can be searched and retrieved electronically. Most academic journals primarily index scholarly journals articles but are not entirely limited to just journal articles. They also include other types of information content, most times in addition to scholarly journal articles (Kenneth O. Irenoa & Sawyerr-george, 2022). Contents of an online database include journal articles, newspapers articles, books reviews and conference proceedings, etc. Online databases are usually updated on a daily, weekly, monthly or quarterly, half yearly or yearly basis. Currently, there are several online database products designed specifically as hosted databases, delivered as software, as a service, or products. Types of online databases are full-text and bibliographic databases. Full-text databases contain the whole content of an article such as citation information, text, illustrations, diagrams and tables. Bibliographic databases only contain citation information of an article, such as author name, journal title, publication date and page numbers. Some of the features of an online database are:

- The online databases are delivered primarily via a web browser
- They are often purchased by a monthly subscription
- They embed common collaboration features such as sharing, e-mail notifications, etc.

Some examples of online databases are: (a) Web of Science; (b) EBSCO; (c) Science Direct; (d) Springer Link; (e) ABI/INFORM; and (f) Scopus. Online databases have made it imperative that we evaluate the awareness level of users towards the online information resources, which will put the Information Managers (Librarians) in a better position to help users, and at the same time give information that will help in evaluating the effectiveness of the services rendered. Abinew and Vuda (2013) survey on acceptance and use of electronic library services in university respondents were asked about their awareness of the available e-library services to indicate their answers by saying "Yes", "No" and "To some extent". Majority of the respondents (57.97%) responded "To some extent" to indicate that they have only limited awareness about the existence of e-libraries resources and didn't know well and in detail. 20.65% of respondents do not know anything about the existence of the e-library services at all. Only 21.38% of the respondents were well aware of the existence of the e-library services. They also found in the same study that there is no significant difference in awareness of e-library services that existed between polytechnics, academic staff and postgraduate students, and among streams (faculties/colleges/institutions).

Egberongbe (2011) surveyed on use and impact of electronic resources at the Delta State University revealed that 80 (71.4%) postgraduate students and 55(78.6%) research scholars were reported in the survey as being aware of e-resources. Awareness of e-resources indicated user knowledge of the availability of the resources, their services and the extent they made use of them. Whereas 32 (28.6%) lecturers and 15 (21.4%) scholars were not aware of electronic information resources, there is no doubt that a larger percentage of the postgraduate students are aware of the availability of electronic information

resources. From observation, majority of the postgraduate students visit internet websites to gain access to electronic information resources.

Tyagi (2011) surveyed on use and awareness of electronic information sources at IIT Roorkee, India found that users have knowledge about the availability of electronic journals, but many use them as the supplementary way to use information. Many users need to be aware of the complete potential of the electronic journals. However, the preference for the electronic format is related to the discipline and age of the respondents and is higher among academic status. The present survey reflects a growing interest in online journals among the user at IIT Roorkee. The study also revealed that most users are aware about the availability of online journals through the library, and they can make maximum use of it for various purposes.

Akpojotor (2016) studied on the awareness and usage of electronic information resources among postgraduate students of library and information science in Southern and Eastern Nigeria revealed that postgraduate students of library and information science are quite aware and highly use electronic information resources. The descriptive survey design was adopted for the study. The census sampling technique was adopted for this study. The questionnaire was used as instrument for data collection. The study also reported that postgraduate LIS students are skilled in the use of electronic information resources. Based on the findings the study concluded that electronic information resources are essential tools for empowering postgraduate students of library and information science in Southern and Eastern Nigeria.

Chimah and Nwokocha (2015) conducted an empirical study of concepts and categories of electronic information resources (EIRs) and how much of them are available in Nigerian Libraries especially in the South East federal polytechnics. A descriptive survey was used for the study. The study adopted questionnaire and semi-structured interview as instruments for data collection. Findings revealed that greater number 65% of postgraduate students from the various polytechnics indicated that they were aware of the available EIRs; whereas the fewer number and percentage 35% respectively indicated their unawareness. Recommendations which include: ICT Infrastructural development, active awareness programme for PG students and Electronic Information literacy programmes were made for improvement.

Aina (2014) surveyed on awareness, accessibility and use of electronic databases among academic staff of Babcock University found that majority of respondents were aware of Academic Journal 59 (69.4%), followed by JSTOR 48 (56.5%) as well as Dissertation and Theses and EBSCOHOST with 46 (54.1) and 43(50.6) respectively. The analysis also revealed that majority of respondents were not aware of Bookboon, World Bank Open Knowledge Repository and National Virtual Library with 22(25.9%), 28 (32.9%) and 25(29.4) respectively. He further concluded that nine out of thirteen databases under consideration were averagely aware by respondents. This implies that there is need to increase awareness to cover all electronic resources the library subscribed to.

Methodology

The research design which was used for this study is the descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey research design seeks to collect data in order to answer questions about current status of the subject or topic. Uzoagulu (2011) noted that in descriptive research, data are usually collected, organized, analyzed and then described as they exist in their natural setting without interference. This design was considered appropriate for this study because the study sought to investigate the actual situation of electronic resources indices and students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko.

The area of the study was the Federal Polytechnic Oko Library, Anambra state, Nigeria. The Main library known as Alex Ekwueme Library is located at the main campus and it has collections for all programmes mounted by the polytechnic. It is the administrative seat of the polytechnic library. It houses an e-library with about 75 desktop computers, the institutional repository and a user's browsing arena. The Main library has a sitting capacity of over 1,000 users concurrently. The e-resources unit houses computers, CDs and diskettes through which the subscribed electronic resources of the university library can be accessed.

The population for both HND I and HND II was 331 students as of when this study was carried out but was narrowed down to 108 students both in HND I and HND II so as to have an accurate and hitch-free result in the School of Information, Library and Information Science. It was derived from the 2021/2022 academic session library register. It covers all students who registered with the polytechnic library.

Table 1: Population Distribution

S/N	Year of Study	Total Number of Registered Students
1.	HND I	52
2.	HND II	56
	Total	108

Source: 2018/2019 Users Statistics Register, Federal Polytechnic Oko, Main Library.

The sample size for this research is 108 students. A purposive sampling technique is used in selecting the respondents from the population of the study. The reason for choosing this sampling technique for the study is that the study population is in a good position to provide relevant information required in actualizing this research. The instrument used for this study is titled "Electronic Resources Awareness and Use by Students Questionnaire" (ERAUSQ). This instrument was self-developed by the researcher based on the research questions and ideas from literatures reviewed on the topic of this study. The questionnaire is made up of three sections; A, B and C. Section A solicits for information for personal data of the respondents, while Section B and C contains the questionnaire items generated in line with the variables. The subjects of the study are required to tick at the appropriate response applicable to them.

The rest of the questions are designed in line with the rating scale and require the respondents to tick any of the options to indicate their level of agreement, and the response mode include the following: Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD).

A total of one hundred and eight (108) copies of the questionnaire were administered to the respondents by the researcher through personal contact and with the aid of research assistance. The researcher with two colleagues, distributed 108 copies of the questionnaires to student respondents in the Federal Polytechnic Oko Library, and waited to collect the completed questionnaire. This is done to ensure high return rate. The data obtained from the questionnaire will be analyzed using mean and standard deviation. T-test will be used in testing the research hypotheses at .05 significance level.

Data Analysis

Data obtained are analyzed using the mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, while t-test is used to test the null hypotheses. The chapter is discussed under the following subheadings: analysis of data, answering of research questions and hypotheses testing, discussion of findings.

Research Question 1: Students' awareness and use of e-books.

Table 2: Summary of responses on the relationship between e-books and students' awareness of online information resources

S/N	Do the following issues influence your awareness of online information resources	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1	E-books are freely available in the library	3.35	0.34	*SA
2	E-books have features which are in a printed book but are easier to use in a digital one (e.g. hyperlinked table of content, or index to the text, bookmarks, annotations)	3.78	0.45	SA
3	E-books have no equivalent printed book available at the library	3.63	0.71	SA
4	E-books at the library ease my search for library resources	3.65	1.2	SA
5	The e-books accessible at the libraries have features that are not available in printed books (e.g. search function, link to dictionaries or a thesaurus)	3.93	0.25	SA
6	The e-book collection at the library are easy to retrieve, making library resource accessible.	3.57	0.81	SA
	Grand Mean Score	3.60	0.62	SA

*SA = Strongly Agree

Table 2 gives the summary of the mean responses for influence of electronics books on students' awareness of online information resources. The result shows that all the items have mean responses above 2.50, the cut-off mean. Since all the items were stated in the positive form, it indicates that e-books have a positive effect on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library.

Research Question 2: Students' awareness and use of online databases.

Table 3: Summary of responses on the influence of online databases on students' awareness of online information resources

S/N	Do the following issues influence your awareness of online information resources	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
1	There are current databases for users in the library	2.22	0.56	*LE
2	The library provides passwords to library users before accessing some database	2.34	0.76	LE
3	Materials gotten from database can be retrieved and saved easily	2.04	0.23	LE
4	Online databases are useful for accessing information	2.12	0.45	LE
5	Online databases are free of charge for students	2.34	0.25	LE
	Grand Mean Score	2.12	0.45	LE

*LE = Less Extent

Table 3 shows the summary of the item by item analysis of the mean responses for influence of online databases on students' awareness of online information resources. The result shows that all the items have mean responses below 2.50, the cut-off mean. Since all the items were stated in the positive form and the grand mean score is 2.12, it indicates that online databases have a negative influence on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. Thus, online databases influence students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library to a less extent.

Hypotheses Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant influence of e-books on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko Library.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis for influence of e-books and students' awareness of online information resources

S/n	Categories	N	Mean \bar{x}	Std dev (σ)	T-cal	Df	T-crit	Decision
1	Ebooks	108	3.60	0.62	3.02	106	1.96	Sig @ 0.5
2	Students' awareness of online information resources	108	3.42	0.71				

The result shows the summary of the t-test analysis for the influence of e-books on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko Library. The result shows that the grand mean score for e-books is 3.60 with a standard deviation score of 0.62, while the mean response for students' awareness of online information resources is 3.42 with a standard deviation score of 0.71. The Table shows that the calculated t, t-cal is 3.02. At 106 degree of freedom and .05 alpha level, the critical t-value is 1.96. Since the t-cal is greater than t-crit, the result is statistically significant and the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is a significant influence of e-books on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant influence of online database on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko Library.

Table 5: Summary of t-test analysis for the influence of online databases on students' awareness of online information resources

S/n	Categories	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Std dev (σ)	T-cal	Df	T-crit	Decision
1	Online databases	108	2.12	0.45	1.87	106	1.96	Not sig @ 0.5
2	Students' awareness of online information resources	108	3.42	0.71				

The result shows the summary of the t-test analysis for the influence of online databases on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. The result shows that the grand mean score for online database is 2.12 with a standard deviation score of 0.45, while the mean response for students' awareness of online information resources is 3.42 with a standard deviation score of 0.71. The Table shows that the calculated t, t-cal is 1.87. At 106 degree of freedom and .05 alpha level, the critical t-value is 1.96. Since the t-cal is less than t-crit, the result is statistically not significant and the null hypothesis is accepted. Thus, there is no significant influence of online database on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library.

Discussion of Findings

The data generated were carefully processed and analyzed. Consequently, the results revealed the following.

E-books and Students' Awareness of Online Information Resources

For research question 1, Table 2 gives the summary of the mean responses for influence of electronics books on students' awareness of online information resources. The result shows that all the items have mean responses above 2.50, the cut-off mean. Since all the items were stated in the positive form, it indicates that e-books have a positive effect on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. The corresponding hypothesis test indicates that there is a significant influence of e-books on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. This finding is line with Ebgerongbe (2011) which found a high extent of user knowledge of availability of e-resources. The research found that majority of students is aware of the benefits of e-books and are actually downloading e-books from the library for their personal consumption.

Online Databases and Students' Awareness of Online Information Resources

From the result of data analyzed, the result shows that all the items have mean responses below 2.50, the cut-off Mean. Since all the items were stated in the positive form and the grand mean score is 2.12, it indicates that online databases have a negative influence on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. Thus, online databases influence students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library to a less extent. The corresponding hypothesis test indicates that there is no significant influence of online databases on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. This finding is supported by Ani and Ahiauzu (2008) which found that the level of awareness of online databases is quite low. This has also reduced patronage of online databases by extension.

Summary of Findings

The researcher studied electronic resources indices and students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. The electronic resources identified are e-books, and online databases. A descriptive survey research design was used and the population of the study comprised all the registered year three and year four undergraduate students of the department of Library and Information Science, school of Information, Federal Polytechnic Oko. The purpose of this study was to find out the level of influence of the various electronic indices on students' awareness of online information resources. The instrument for the study was a questionnaire designed in line with the 4-point rating Scale. The validation of the research instrument was carried out by the supervisor. The sample size comprised of one hundred and eight (108) undergraduate students and the method of data analysis was the mean and standard deviation for answering of the research questions and t-test for the testing of the research hypotheses.

Conclusion

While funds and funding of academic libraries still remains a key issue for a foreseeable future due to the perception of academics, librarians and management of tertiary institutions on the roles libraries play in the teaching, learning and research (Irenea, Bribena & Eru, 2019), subscription and use of electronic resources by students will continue to remain a challenge that must be surmounted. The challenge of making access to these resources available and accessible to students for their research and learning pursuit, requires effort on the part of the library to inform and create adequate awareness to the students on the subscribed electronic resources. Based on the result and findings of this study, it is concluded that electronic resources indices have a significant influence on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. E-books which are electronic resources are being used extensively by students to access online information resources needed for study and research, and also have a positive influence on students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko main library. In addition, online databases are known to be vital sources of information and provided by the library but they influence students' awareness of online information resources in the Federal Polytechnic Oko Library to a less extent. Increasing awareness and training of students on how to use electronic resources is crucial. When this is done, it is equally important to make those resources accessible to students. In conclusion, recommendations on how to alleviate the problems of electronic resources indices and students' awareness of online information resources were made. Based on the findings of this study, the researcher has made the following recommendations.

Recommendations

1. Libraries should intensify their awareness campaigns concerning the availability of e- books in the library and motivate students to greater use of online information resources for their academic and research work.
2. Information and communication technology training programme should be given to all the first-year students as a course of study as this will help to educate the students in the use of e-journals for academic purposes.
3. Library administrators should make efforts to improve access and create more awareness to more online databases to ensure access to more online information resources for students.

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